

Deliverable report

NOVA (WP2)

D-2.3.3. (D-JRP6-2.6)

**Case control study of food
risk factors for sporadic
Salmonella infections**

JRP6 - NOVA - FBZ1 - 1st Call

Responsible Partner: SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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WP and task	JRP6-WP2-T3 NOVA-WP2: Analysis of food purchase data. Task 3: Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease
Leader	SSI (DK)
Other contributors	
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<p>Dissemination</p> <p><i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i></p>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
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CASE CONTROL STUDY OF FOOD RISK FACTORS FOR SPORADIC SALMONELLA INFECTIONS TOOL

0. Please note

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, work on this project was paused for a significant amount of time and did not finish within the NOVA project period. However, the work continues and will be concluded in the coming months. The work and its results will be published, and two papers are planned (of which one exists in draft). This deliverable therefore only briefly describes the status of the project.

1. Introduction

With this study, we wish to examine risk factors for sporadic salmonellosis by a novel method. We plan to do a case-control study, where we, rather than using questionnaires, ask people to collect their consumer purchase data, in order to compare the food items and food groups cases buy and compare those to the purchases of a comparable control population. The study is designed as a proof-of-concept study for utilizing consumer purchase data (CPD) in case control studies, and further to possibly identify risk factors for sporadic disease using only CPD.

Salmonella was chosen as the model organism and the project concerned Denmark only. To be able to do the study, we have first aimed to build a digital solution into which Danish residents by invitation (cases of salmonella and comparable persons without known infection selected from the Danish population register) can sign up. This solution includes a way of safely logging in to a secure website where the user is presented with study objectives, and information about legal rights and with the possibility of further opening up for investigator access, into past purchase records. This is possible if the user is already subscribing to a third party solution (an app) that stores the results of credit card purchases – which approximately 20% of the Danish population is. This technical solution (which was built with additional support from funding outside of NOVA) is now working and is legally compliant. The web-portal was described in D-2.3.1. “Description of data infrastructure module, including an electronic informed consent tool”. Please see figure 1.

Construction it has involved overcoming a large number of practical, technical and legal

challenges previously identified in D-2.1.2, “Description by member state of barriers for use: legal, political, economic, practical and technical obstacles”.

2. Methods

For the case-control study itself, a detailed project description has been made. Invitation letters have been produced. The study has been approved by The Danish Data Protection Agency and SSI Compliance, journal nr.: 21/00801. In addition, a manuscript draft of a study protocol entitled “protocol for a case-control study using an e-consent tool to collect consumer purchase data in Denmark” has been prepared. The manuscript describes the data collection portal and the planned study.

In brief, we will make use of postal invitations (using the Danish electronic postal system, e-Boks) to invite participants. Participants include prior salmonella cases, excluding known travel cases, spanning 2019-2021, and matched control persons. Controls are selected from the Danish Population Register (CPR) with matching on age and gender. Only invitees that are using the digital receipts solution used in the data collection platform are eligible as participants.

Due to the exceptional COVID-19 situation, the legal and technical approval by SSI compliance, of the data collection platform, was delayed until early June 2021. Since then, a silent release of the solution has been conducted, with 16 pilot participant's onboarded, and more than 8000 receipts collected. As a result of the delayed approval, running the case control study has been postponed. We aim to run a pilot phase in December 2021, testing digital invitational letters and onboarding, and to send out the invitations for the full study in the first months of 2022.

The analysis will consist of the comparison of purchases between cases and controls, calculating odds ratios and their confidence intervals as a measure of association. Food purchases will be structured into different levels of food groups (from particular to general, such as 'pork') and analysed accordingly, taking frequencies of buying the products into account. Food consumption profiles will be constructed and will constitute an additional level of analysis. Cases of known outbreaks (all isolates of salmonella cases in Denmark are whole genome sequenced, and outbreak investigations performed for most clusters) will be used for corroborative purposes. A model of risk factors will be aimed for.

3. Results & Discussion

Not yet available. As mentioned, data collection is scheduled to begin in December 2021 and the project to be finalised within 2022. The results shall be published in a peer-reviewed journal. Expected outcomes in terms of publications, are thus: Protocol/register description paper, and a paper of the study results. We hope that the study, since it is in many ways groundbreaking, will be of interest to the scientific foodborne infections community. However, we do not know how many people would want to participate – a low participation rate is seen as a potential risk of the study.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the landing site of the consumer purchase data collection platform at mineindkob.dk. For further description, please visit the site or refer to D-2.3.1. "Description of data infrastructure module, including an electronic informed consent tool".